

"THEORETICAL IDEAS AND REFLECTIONS ON THE CONCEPT AND CLASSIFICATION OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF MEDICAL SERVICES IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN."

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Abstract: This research work identified the necessary measures to organize primary health care in our country in order to create more favorable conditions for the population to use quality medical services. Special approaches and proposals were made to expand the possibilities of providing remote medical services to the population using modern information technologies, to unite all medical associations in our country, and to improve the quality of medical services.

Keywords: medical services, online appointment at clinics, emergency medical care, service delivery tool, quality of medical services, convenience of remote medical services, medical insurance.

Introduction

The current rapidly developing medical technologies are closely related to all aspects of healthcare. This applies to the obstetric system, perinatal and neonatal surveillance, medical examinations and professional examinations, the preventive system in all types of medical care, work with people with disabilities, etc.

In the Republic of Uzbekistan and abroad, science is actively discussing the issues of digital transformation in healthcare and increasing the efficiency of organizing medical services in the context of the emergence of unprecedented new pandemic threats. ¹One of the priorities of state policy is the formation of a healthy lifestyle, the preservation and strengthening of the health of the population based on ensuring the availability and quality of medical care; ensuring effective state regulation and guaranteeing the provision of modern free medical care to all residents; much work is being done to reorient healthcare towards comprehensive diagnostics, prevention and treatment in the early stages of the disease.

Improving the efficiency of medical care should be based on the concept of a

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healthy lifestyle, the concept of ensuring the convenience and quality of medical care. In this article, taking into account the goals and objectives of the study, we will consider the factors affecting the activities of medical services and their characteristics, as well as conceptual approaches to improving the quality of medical services.

Literature review

The problem of the quality of medical services has been studied by the World Health Organization (WHO) and the following scientists: L.A. Belovoy, G.F. Valeevoy, M.V. Vertiy, O.V. Vlasovoy, O.A. Gouge, M. ... A. V. Emanuel, M. Q. Pardayev, A. P. Khazratov, Z. S. Ortikov, M. M. Mukhammedov, B. Abdukarimov, N. U. Normurodov, R. O'. Dosnazarovich.

Materials and Methods

The research process used the methods of systematic analysis, analysis and synthesis, induction and deduction, logical approach, selective observation, economic-mathematical, statistical, and economic analysis.

Results and Discussion

The aging of the population significantly increases the need for medical care. In addition, modern medical care is being implemented on the basis of the latest scientific achievements and various types of medical equipment. The increase in the proportion of the elderly population creates a number of socio-medical problems. This may lead to an increase in the need for more intensive medical care, such as inpatient treatment and external assistance (including its technical equipment), taking into account the characteristics of older people, and the need to develop a healthy lifestyle and find ways to provide additional financing for the social sphere, as well as the health sector. In recent years, such problems have been attracting increasing attention from researchers and practitioners. A study conducted in 2019 by scientists from the Higher School of Economics and experts from the World Bank Group on the specific needs of the elderly population for medical and social services is noteworthy. In particular, a number of obstacles to obtaining medical care were identified, including the lack of medical equipment for diagnostics and treatment in state polyclinics. Interestingly, this problem was noted by both healthcare consumers and clinicians. From the point of view of the medical equipment market, this indicates a low efficiency of state regulation of the provision of medical equipment to healthcare institutions. According to statistics, with an increase in the number of elderly people, the number of ambulance calls is increasing significantly, while the number of initial calls is significantly decreasing

(according to the authors of the study, due to distrust in the healthcare system). Consequently, due to the aging of the population, the need for medical equipment is increasing day by day, on the one hand, equipment for emergency care and inpatient care is required, and on the other hand, diagnostic equipment needs to be improved and, above all, increased.

Table 1.1: Volume of medical services in the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan (created by the authors based on data compiled by the State Statistics Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan)

Volume of medical services					
Years	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023
All, in billions of soums	3104,3	3386,7	5105,9	6613,1	8441,2

Conclusion

Mamlakatimizdagi raqamli iqtisodiyot sharoitida sog'liqni saqlash sohasidagi tibbiy xizmatlarini iqtisodiyotda samarali rivojlantirish va samaradorligini oshirish mamlakatimizda dolzarb masalalardan iborat bo'lib hisoblanadi. Mazkur maqolada masofaviy tibbiy xizmatni rivojlantirish orqali tibbiyot sohasini davlat tomonidan tartibga solish mexanizmini takomillashtirish sohasidagi nazariy va amaliy tadqiqotlar asosida quyidagi xulosa va tavsiyalar ishlab chiqildi:

Xorijda va mamlakatimizda tibbiy xizmat ko'rsatish sohasini rivojlantirish holati tahlili davlat nazorati tizimida kasalliklar sonining ko'payishining oldini

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olish bo'yicha profilaktika chora-tadbirlarini amalga oshirish alohida ahamiyat kasb etishini ko'rsatdi. Mamlakatimizda aholi o'rtasida kasalliklarning ko'payishi o'rtacha umr ko'rish davomiyligining qisqarishi bilan birga, iqtisodiy faol aholi orasidan odamlarning mehnatga layoqatlilik davrining qisqarishiga olib kelmoqda.

Tibbiy xizmat ko'rsatish sohasining samarali faoliyat yuritishining eng muhim sharti – bu sodir bo'layotgan jarayonlarni tartibga solishning samarali vositalarining mavjudligi, aholi va tibbiyot tashkilotlari, shuningdek, sug'urta kompaniyalari va davlatning o'zaro munosabatlarni takomillashtirishdan manfaatdorligidir. Sog'liqni saqlash sohasida davlat-xususiy sheriklik loyihalarini amalga oshirishning afzalliklari ta'kidlangan va asoslantirilgan:²

Tibbiy xizmat ko'rsatish sohasida mamlakatimizda sog'liqni saqlashni rivojlantirish jarayonlari ishtirokchilarining o'zaro hamkorligini oshirish uchun davlat-xususiy sheriklik asosida taklif etilayotgan ixtisoslashtirilgan masofaviy tibbiy xizmat ko'rsatish tizimini joriy etish loyihalarini ishlab chiqish va ilgari surish yo'nalishlarida shakllantirish zarur.

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